

Curcumin Derivatives for Alzheimer's Disease: Structure-Activity Relationships, Predictive Physicochemical Parameters and Molecular Docking

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ABSTRACT: Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder linked to amyloid- β plaques, tau tangles, and oxidative stress. Curcumin has shown potential in targeting these issues, but its poor bioavailability and limited ability to cross the blood-brain barrier reduce its effectiveness. This study explores Structure-Activity Relationships (SAR) described in literature and relates them to results obtained in a study where the therapeutic potential of curcumin derivatives was assessed. Using computational tools, key physicochemical properties of those derivatives were analyzed. The derivatives were also used in a molecular docking experiment. Experimental findings helped validate the previously established structure-activity relationships and helped provide a future perspective of possible structural modifications to obtain new analogs with greater therapeutic potential.

1. Introduction

1.1 Alzheimer's Disease (AD)

Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is currently recognized as one of the most prevalent forms of dementia in the elderly population [1]. It is classified as a mental and behavioral disorder, significantly contributing to the loss of independence in affected individuals. Approximately 50 million people worldwide live with dementia, and this number is projected to double by 2050 [2], correlating with increased life expectancy globally. Aging is the primary risk factor for AD, with incidence doubling every five years after the age of 65. AD is a progressive and irreversible neurological disorder characterized by memory loss, executive dysfunction, and alterations in social behavior [3].

Several hallmarks are associated with AD, including neurochemical alterations, senile plaque formation (aggregates of amyloid- β peptide [$A\beta$]), neuroinflammation, oxidative stress, and hyperphosphorylated tau protein. Dysregulation of neurotransmitter levels, such as acetylcholine (ACh), is observed since the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus regions predominantly populated by cholinergic neurons—are most affected in early disease stages [4]. The most used symptomatic treatments for AD, such as donepezil, rivastigmine, and galantamine, act by inhibiting acetylcholinesterase, the enzyme responsible for ACh metabolism, thereby increasing ACh levels in the synaptic cleft [5].

The aggregation of $A\beta$ peptides, which consist of 40 to 42 amino acid residues, leads to the formation of neurotoxic extracellular senile plaques. These peptides result from the abnormal cleavage of the amyloid precursor protein (APP), a membrane protein. APP can be cleaved through two pathways: the non-amyloidogenic α -pathway or the amyloidogenic β -pathway [6]. In the first, APP is hydrolyzed by α -secretase, and in the α -pathway, APP is hydrolyzed by α -secretase and subsequently by γ -secretase, resulting in soluble, non-toxic peptides. Conversely, in the β -pathway, APP is hydrolyzed by β -secretase

(Beta-site APP Cleaving Enzyme 1, BACE1) and γ -secretase, leading to insoluble, neurotoxic peptides. High concentrations of these peptides form senile plaques, causing neuronal atrophy and eventual cell death [7].

Tau protein is associated with neuronal microtubules, which form part of the cytoskeleton and facilitate organelle transport. Tau stabilizes these microtubules [8]. In AD, tau protein is phosphorylated by glycogen synthase kinase-3 (GSK-3), a serine/threonine kinase, causing its dissociation from microtubules and aggregation into neurofibrillary tangles, disrupting nerve impulse conduction [9].

Oxidative stress results from an imbalance between the production and accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the cellular capacity to neutralize these compounds. Excess ROS, which are neurotoxic, are not adequately eliminated by cellular antioxidant systems. For instance, nitric oxide (NO), produced by nitric oxide synthase (NOS), induces synaptic alterations due to its neurotoxicity [10]. This oxidative stress may stem from A β accumulation, interactions with metal ions, mitochondrial dysfunction critical to ROS regulation, or the induction of inflammatory responses.

Neuroinflammation, another hallmark of AD, is mediated by microglia and astrocytes [11]. Microglia, the resident macrophages of the central nervous system (CNS), exhibit heightened activity in AD patients, with their concentrations around senile plaques (A β aggregates) being two to five times higher [12]. A β peptides act as danger signals, or damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs), which bind to microglial receptors such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs), activating microglia and triggering an inflammatory response characterized by the release of pro-inflammatory mediators, including neurotoxic cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-12, and IL-18 [13]. This inflammatory component of AD involves local cytokine-mediated responses, complement cascade activation, and the induction of enzyme systems such as iNOS and COX-2 [6].

Current therapeutic options for AD neither reverse nor cure the disease; they only address symptoms and slow progression. This limitation is primarily due to an incomplete understanding of the complex molecular mechanisms underlying AD. Consequently, there is significant interest in developing new molecules capable of targeting the multiple hallmarks of the disease.

1.2 Curcumin

Curcumin is a natural molecule and polyphenol derived from turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), widely used in Indian cuisine. Discovered in the 19th century, curcumin's health benefits have been extensively studied.

Its chemical name is [1,7-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione], with a molecular mass of 368.38 g/mol. This polyphenol exhibits keto-enol tautomerism (Figure 1), where the keto form predominates at pH < 7, and the enol form at pH > 7 [14].

Curcumin displays anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities and interferes with amyloid- β (A β) aggregation, making it a compound of therapeutic interest in Alzheimer's Disease (AD) [15].

Curcumin is believed to possess anti-amyloidogenic properties that hinder peptide aggregation into amyloid plaques. This assumption is backed by multiple *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies demonstrating that curcumin not only prevents the formation of amyloid aggregates but also destabilizes those that have already developed, thereby reducing their size through interactions with A β ₁₋₄₀ and A β ₁₋₄₂ peptides [43].

The underlying mechanism has been attributed to interactions between curcumin's keto group and the aromatic rings of A β dimers, as well as the binding of its polar hydroxyl groups to the polar pockets of A β peptides, which contributes to the disassembly of amyloid aggregates [44]. Moreover, *in vivo* research conducted on nematodes has revealed that curcumin enhances the levels of acetylated α -tubulin, a key indicator of microtubule stabilization. This finding suggests that curcumin may counteract tau hyperphosphorylation by reinforcing microtubule stability, ultimately reducing tau-induced toxicity.

Additionally, Curcumin demonstrates significant neuroprotective properties by modulating neuroinflammatory pathways, scavenging reactive oxygen species, and inhibiting the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines [49]. It also acts as an antioxidant that can neutralize free radicals, which are compounds that can cause oxidative stress and damage to cells. By reducing oxidative stress in the brain, curcumin can help protect neurons and maintain cognitive function [50]. Furthermore, Curcumin has metal-chelating properties, meaning it can bind to metals such as iron and copper that may contribute to amyloid aggregation and oxidative stress in the brain. This chelation can help reduce the toxic effects of these metals and protect brain health [51].

Due to its lipophilicity, curcumin may cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB), demonstrating neuroprotective activity, but its permeability is very low. Its pharmacokinetic profile is also relatively weak. Curcumin exhibits low oral bioavailability (up to 1%), which limits its potential therapeutic application [16]. The low bioavailability of curcumin is primarily attributed to poor intestinal absorption, low solubility, and extensive hepatic metabolism through reduction and conjugation reactions. After conjugation with glucuronic acid (a Phase II reaction), curcumin loses its ability to cross the BBB. Consequently, orally administered curcumin is poorly absorbed into the bloodstream, leading to low brain concentrations and limited efficacy in treating AD [17].

Its poor pharmacokinetic profile and its reduced BBB permeability result in a limited amount of curcumin capable of reaching the brain. The development of curcumin analogs is, therefore, an area of significant interest to address its low bioavailability and improve its stability and efficacy in the context of AD.

The present study describes Structure-Activity Relationships described in literature and analyses the results of curcumin derivatives studied in the group of Professor Sónia Santos (FFUC and ICBR) to try to confirm those relationships. One of those derivatives is capable of mimicking and exceeding the efficacy of curcumin [45]. Only activities with interest regarding AD were considered.

Figure 1. Keto-enol tautomerism of curcumin.

2. Materials and methods

Structure-Activity Relationship (SAR). An observational study of structure-activity relationships described in the literature was conducted, focusing on the various activities of curcumin and its derivatives. Articles referencing activities relevant to Alzheimer's Disease (AD) were filtered and selected. The electronic search was performed using the PubMed database with

the following keywords: *curcumin, curcumin derivatives, structure-activity relationship, curcumin's biological activities, Alzheimer's Disease, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, A β aggregation inhibitors.*

No time frame was set for the search to avoid excluding relevant studies. The earliest studies addressing curcumin's activity in AD date back to 1998, and the available information on curcumin's activities is relatively recent.

Prediction of Physicochemical Properties. The physicochemical properties influencing the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of the curcuminoid derivatives under study were predicted using the SwissADME program. The SMILES codes of the compounds' structures, generated with ChemDraw, were inputted into the software.

Docking. The 3D structures of curcumin, derivative 1, derivative 4 and compound BF1 were docked onto amyloid peptides extracted from the crystallographic structures of A β (1-40) (PDB ID: 2M4J, [54]) and A β (1-42) (PDB ID: 2MXU, [55]). Which were retrieved from RCSB Protein Data Bank [56]. The molecular complexes between the A β and the studied molecules were obtained through a standard docking using SeeSAR [57].

The curcumin derivatives were synthesized by Professor Maria Robalo's group (ISEL) and studied by Professor Sónia Silva's group (FFUC and ICBR).

3. Structure-activity relationships of curcumin derivatives

3.1 Anti-aggregant activity A β

Amyloid- β (A β) peptide aggregation, resulting in the formation of insoluble and neurotoxic senile plaques, is one of the primary hallmarks of Alzheimer's Disease (AD). Curcumin has been shown to inhibit A β peptide aggregation and is also capable of disassembling preformed plaques [18]. Furthermore, it significantly reduces the toxicity of A β oligomers [19].

A molecular dynamics study simulating the nucleation process of 12 peptides revealed that curcumin interacts with plaques by intercalating into the A β chains. It binds strongly through hydrogen bonding, van der Waals forces, π - π interactions, and Michael addition reactions, where the unsaturated diketone acts as the acceptor and the -OH (hydroxyl) and -SH (thiol) groups of amino acids serve as donors [20, 14]. These interactions disrupt the stabilizing interactions between amino acid residues in the A β polypeptide chain and break interactions between A β peptides, shifting the equilibrium toward non-toxic aggregates. Curcumin binds to these peptides and interferes with their native structure, preventing further aggregation.

Key structural features of curcumin, including its keto-enol group, phenolic groups, methoxy groups on the aromatic rings, and the rigid (planar) structure derived from extensive conjugation, contribute to its anti-aggregation activity against A β . Indeed, a study evaluating the ability of various curcumin analogs to inhibit insoluble plaque formation concluded that the best inhibitors possessed aromatic rings substituted with a methoxy group (-OCH₃) and a hydroxyl group (-OH), like curcumin. These groups are positioned *para* relative to the seven-carbon unsaturated spacer and *ortho* to each other.

Interestingly, replacing the hydroxyl group with another methoxy group enhances A β aggregation inhibition by six to seven times compared to curcumin [21]. This substitution may improve

curcumin's bioavailability by preventing hepatic conjugation reactions, which increase solubility and lead to faster and easier excretion. Additionally, this substitution reduces the compound's polarity, increasing its solubility in membrane lipids and enhancing passive diffusion across the blood-brain barrier (BBB).

The rigidity of the unsaturated carbon spacer between the phenyl groups is also essential for activity. Reducing this group results in the loss of anti-aggregation activity [22], this indicates that the structural rigidity of curcumin and its analogs is crucial, as it destabilizes A β peptide aggregates by interfering with their flexibility.

In another study analyzing anti-aggregation activity, two curcumin analogs were synthesized with substitutions at the central carbon of the methylene group. One compound contained a carboxyl group (FMeC2), while the other had an ester group (FMeC1) (Figure 2). The carboxyl-substituted compound showed no effect on A β aggregates, whereas the ester-substituted derivative significantly reduced the levels of soluble and insoluble amyloid (A β 40 and A β 42). It also inhibited the formation of high-molecular-weight A β aggregates, increasing the quantity of low-molecular-weight aggregates, which are less cytotoxic [23].

The ester group on the central carbon enhances A β anti-aggregation activity, as the derivative with this functional group showed greater activity than curcumin at the same equimolar concentration, demonstrating superior pharmacological efficacy. However, since esters are hydrolyzed by esterases (enzymes that catalyze ester hydrolysis) in various tissues, it is expected that this group will be cleaved, rendering the carboxylated derivative unable to cross the BBB.

An interesting approach would be to replace the ester group with a bioisostere resistant to hydrolysis, potentially improving the compound's pharmacokinetic properties and therapeutic efficacy.

Figure 2. FMeC1 and FMeC2 structure; (Yanagisawa, D. et al 2014 [23]).

3.2 Anti-inflammatory activity

Numerous studies have demonstrated that curcumin exhibits significant anti-inflammatory activity. This activity is attributed to its ability to inhibit transcription factors such as nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B), which regulates the expression of pro-inflammatory genes [24]. Curcumin inhibits NF- κ B activity by activating peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR γ), which prevents the degradation of I κ B, thereby blocking the nuclear translocation of NF- κ B [25]. Additionally, curcumin reduces the activity of cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), an enzyme in the arachidonic acid cascade responsible for producing prostaglandins [26].

Curcumin also binds to and inhibits 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX), an enzyme involved in leukotriene synthesis, which mediates pro-inflammatory responses [27]. Lastly, curcumin inhibits the

expression of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) and pro-inflammatory cytokines, including tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-1 (IL-1), IL-6, and IL-8 [25].

A study comparing the anti-inflammatory activities of dimethoxycurcumin (DiMC), curcumin, bisdimethoxycurcumin (BDMC), and tetrahydrocurcumin (THC) evaluated their ability to inhibit nitric oxide (NO) production by iNOS, suppress iNOS expression, and reduce NF- κ B activity. The findings revealed that all compounds, except THC, exhibited these activities. DiMC was the most effective in inhibiting NO production, iNOS expression, and NF- κ B activation, followed by curcumin and BDMC [28]. This suggests that increasing the number of methoxy groups on the aromatic rings of curcumin, along with its conjugated double bonds, enhances its anti-inflammatory activity. These structural features also improve its anti-amyloid β (A β) aggregation activity and contribute to better bioavailability [29].

Pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β , play critical roles in inflammation associated with various diseases, including AD [30]. These cytokines are overexpressed in AD and are produced by activated microglia and astrocytes. When cells are exposed to cytokines like TNF- α , they activate NF- κ B, leading to the expression of pro-inflammatory genes, including *COX-2*, *LOX-2*, and *iNOS*. Therefore, agents capable of suppressing the overexpression of these cytokines could serve as potential therapeutic agents for AD [29]. Curcumin has been shown to inhibit the transcription of these cytokines in microglial cells in a dose-dependent manner, further contributing to its anti-inflammatory activity [31].

3.3 Antioxidant Activity

Curcumin exhibits antioxidant activity, acting as an excellent scavenger of ROS, which is important for its therapeutic actions, particularly in Alzheimer's Disease (AD), where oxidative stress is present [10]. These species consist of free radicals such as peroxide (O_2^{2-}), superoxide (O_2^-), among others, or simply oxidizing molecules that cause the oxidation of other molecules through hydrogen atom abstraction, electron transfer, and radical transfer. These types of reactions can occur in the phenolic groups and the α,β -unsaturated diketone of curcumin, as these groups are responsible for the antioxidant activity of the molecule. The most easily removed hydrogen in reactions with free radicals is from the phenolic groups, making this the group that contributes the most to the antioxidant activity [14]. Radicals are formed, which, due to the extensive conjugation of the π -system, are stabilized by resonance [32]. Furthermore, curcumin forms complexes with metal ions, such as Al^{3+} , an ion associated with the progression of AD, which makes A β aggregates more toxic and leads to oxidative stress [33]. The chelation effect of curcumin, derived from its α,β -unsaturated diketone group, thus contributes to its antioxidant activity and therapeutic action in AD.

A study of curcumin's antioxidant activity using a DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) test showed that the presence of hydroxyl groups in the *para* position relative to the phenyl groups is a requirement for the antioxidant activity of curcumin, as well as electron-donating groups in the *ortho* positions, such as the methoxy group [34].

According to another study, although curcumin analogs substituted with -OH groups on the phenyl groups show greater antioxidant activity, -OCH₃ groups in the *ortho* position significantly facilitate hydrogen abstraction from the hydroxyl group, as an intramolecular hydrogen-bonding interaction is established between these two groups [35]. Additionally, the methoxy group in the *ortho* position stabilizes the phenoxyl free radical, contributing to enhanced free radical scavenging activity [36]. This increased stability is due to the nature of the methoxy group as an electron donor, which, by

donating electron density to the adjacent carbon, allows pairing with the unpaired electron of the radical.

Additionally, tacrine-curcumin hybrid derivatives showed pronounced antioxidant activity, and positive metal-ions chelating ability *in vitro*, which makes them potential compound to halt ion-induced A β aggregation, since there are evidence that demonstrate that the misfolding progress associated with A β accumulation was greatly influenced by ions [52]. It was shown that the presence or absence of specific functional groups, such as the phenolic hydroxyl group, impacts antioxidant activity. For example, a compound lacking this group showed significantly weaker activity, indicating that this specific structure is crucial for the desired biological effects. Results indicated that curcumin was a potent radical scavenger of peroxy radicals, an activity that was attributed to its enol and phenolic hydroxyl groups. Also, the inclusion of a β -diketone structure in some hybrids was associated with improved metal ions-chelating ability. This ability to bind metal ions may be beneficial for halting amyloid beta aggregation and aid in Alzheimer's treatment, enhancing the overall therapeutic profile of the hybrids [53].

It was also found that mono-substituted analogs on the central methylene group of the α,β -unsaturated diketone, without substitutions on the phenyl groups, exhibit antioxidant activity by forming radicals on a tertiary carbon stabilized by hyperconjugation and resonance effects [37]. Thus, the presence of a tertiary carbon in the center of the seven-carbon spacer will also contribute to the antioxidant activity.

Table 1. Summary of structure-activity relationships	
Activity	Functional groups contributing to activity
Anti-A β aggregation	Hydroxyl groups on aromatic rings, α,β -unsaturated diketone group, and extensive conjugation of the π -system.
	Methoxy group in the ortho position relative to the hydroxyl group; substitution of the hydroxyl group with another methoxy increases anti-aggregation activity against A β .
	Reduction of the double bonds in the seven-carbon "linker" between phenyl groups eliminates this activity.
	Methylene group in the central carbon, with an ester substituent, enhances anti-aggregation activity against A β .
Anti-inflammatory	Substitution of the hydroxyl group on the phenyl group with a methoxy group increases anti-inflammatory activity (NO production, iNOS expression, NF-kB activation).
	Reduction of the double bonds in the seven-carbon "linker" between phenyl groups eliminates this activity.
Antioxidant	Phenol groups in the para position provide the greatest contribution to this activity.
	The α,β -unsaturated diketone group contributes to antioxidant activity through chelation effects.
	Methoxy group in the ortho position contributes to antioxidant activity by being an electron density donor and establishing an intramolecular hydrogen bond with the hydroxyl group.
	Mono-substitution on the central carbon in the methylene group contributes to antioxidant activity through the formation of a radical on a tertiary carbon.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Physicochemical characteristics of a set of synthetic curcumin derivatives

In this study, the physicochemical properties of curcumin and six curcumin derivatives (derivatives 1-6) were explored using the SwissADME program. These compounds were synthesized in the group of Professor Maria Robalo (ISEL) and studied in the group of Professor Sónia Santos (FFUC and ICBR). The general compounds' structure can be seen in figure.3.

Figure 3. General structure of derivatives 1-6. With the R moieties varying between compounds. R₁ and R₅: -OH, -OCH₃, -H; R₂ and R₆: -OH, -OCH₃, -H; R₃ and R₇: -OCH₃; R₄: -CH₂CO₂H, -CH₂CO₂C(CH₃)₃, -H₂.

After designing the chemical structures using appropriate software (ChemDraw) and obtaining their respective SMILES codes, these were input into the SwissADME program to gather information about their physicochemical properties, such as the molecular weight of the compounds, their polar surface area (PSA), and the number of hydrogen bond acceptors and donors.

Pharmacokinetic properties, including lipophilicity (LogPo/w), blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, and gastrointestinal absorption, were also predicted. The ability to inhibit or enhance the activity of hepatic cytochrome P450 enzymes was assessed. Additionally, it was verified whether the compounds comply with Lipinski's rule of five. The results of these predictions are presented in Table 2.

According to the predictions, most of the compounds are unlikely to cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB), which contradicts experimental results previously obtained by Professor Sónia Santos' group for some compounds, such as derivative 4, derivative 1, and synthetic curcumin. Based on the PAMPA (Parallel Artificial Membrane Permeability Assay) test, these compounds do cross the BBB (unpublished data). The prediction by SwissADME relies on the BOILED-Egg model (Brain Or Intestinal Estimated permeation method), which predicts both gastrointestinal absorption and BBB penetration for small molecules. The accuracy of this method for predicting BBB diffusion is 88% and is based on PSA and LogPo/w [38]. Therefore, an error exists in the program's prediction regarding the diffusion of molecules across the BBB. Discrepancies in the model's prediction may

stem from technical issues leading to suboptimal classification of certain molecules' lipophilicity and polarity.

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of the proposed new derivatives, obtained through Swiss-ADME								
Compounds	Physicochemical Properties			Pharmacokinetics				Druglikeness
	MW (g/mol)	H-bond acceptors/donors	ASP (Å ²)	LogP _{o/w}	GI absorption	BBB	CYP450 inhibitor	Lipinski (violations)
Curcumin	368.38	6/2	93.06	3.03	High	No	Yes, 2C9 and 3A4	0
Derivative 1	368.38	6/2	93.06	2.96	High	No	Yes, 2C9 and 3A4	0
Derivative 2	426.42	8/3	130.36	2.65	High	No	Yes, 2C9 and 3A4	0
Derivative 3	482.52	8/2	119.36	3.89	High	No	Yes, 2C9, 2D6 AND 3A4	0
Derivative 4	482.52	8/2	119.36	3.880	High	No	Yes, 2C9, 2D6 and 3A4	0
Derivative 5	458.50	8/2	111.52	3.82	High	No	Yes, 2C9 and 3A4	0
Derivative 6	308.33	4/2	111.52	3.82	High	No	Yes, 2C9 and 3A4	0

4.2 Analysis of the experimental results of derivatives 1 and 4

Among all the synthetic curcumin derivatives studied, derivatives 1 and 4 showed the best *in vitro* results related to Alzheimer's disease (AD) (unpublished data). Derivative 1 has the same functional groups as curcumin but with reversed substitutions on the aromatic rings; that is, the methoxy group is in the *para* position, and the hydroxyl group is in the *ortho* position. Derivative 4 has the same modification in the aromatic ring, along with a substitution of the central carbon in the α,β -unsaturated diketone with a tert-butoxide group.

Some experimental results confirm the structure-activity relationships previously discussed. Using the DPPH assay, one of the most commonly used methods to assess antioxidant activity due to its high sensitivity and simplicity [39], it was observed that Derivative 4 displayed lower antioxidant activity than curcumin [45], and that, in turn, Derivative 1 had less activity in the ABTS assay than derivative 4. This confirms the importance of a hydroxyl group in the *para* position on the phenyl group and shows that compounds with a substituted central carbon contribute to antioxidant activity through the formation of radicals on tertiary carbons.

According to a recent study made by Professor Sónia Silva's group, the antioxidant activity of Derivative 4 is, however, due to Nrf2 activation [45]. Additionally, Derivative 4 contributes to an increase in HO-1 (Heme Oxygenase 1) protein levels, whose neuroprotective effect seems to be dependent on concomitant Nrf2 activation [46]. Through Nrf2 activation, Derivative 4 stimulates the expression of antioxidant enzymes and promotes a decrease in pro-inflammatory cytokines levels, in a similarly to curcumin [47].

In assays evaluating anti-inflammatory activity in a microglial cell line using the Griess reaction, which quantifies nitric oxide (NO) production [40], a mediator of inflammation at high concentrations [41], it was found that Derivative 4 showed greater efficacy than derivative 1, and both were more effective than curcumin in significantly reducing NO production at equimolar concentrations (unpublished data). Derivative 4 also demonstrated greater potency than Derivative 1, as a lower concentration was required to achieve better results, suggesting that the tert-butyl ester group plays an important role in its anti-inflammatory action. Furthermore, Derivative 1 also reduced *in vitro* protein levels of iNOS and Pro-IL-1 β , similar to Derivative 4, although the latter also reduced COX-2 protein levels, showing significant anti-inflammatory activity.

These results suggest that the cellular and molecular mechanisms of Derivative 4 and curcumin do not overlap, since both are capable of inhibiting pro-inflammatory mediators, but curcumin's anti-inflammatory activity is due to its ability to inhibit NF- κ B signaling pathway [45].

Regarding the amyloidogenic cascade, both curcumin and derivative 1 significantly reduced A β 42 levels *in vitro* at the same comparative concentrations (unpublished data) in the N2a-APP_{swe} cell line. This cell line carries the Swedish mutation, a mutation in the gene encoding APP that leads to increased production and secretion of A β [42]. Derivative 4 showed no effect on this cell line. However, it significantly reduced A β 40 and A β 42 levels in the hippocampus and plasma of APP/PS1 transgenic animals, which express human APP with mutations associated with AD [45]. This indicates that while it does not show effects *in vitro*, it does impact the amyloidogenic cascade *in vivo*.

Thus, Derivative 4 shows good results, and it appears to be a good alternative to curcumin in AD's treatment, since it increased antioxidant enzymes levels, decreased inflammatory markers, and inhibited *in vitro* formation of A β aggregates in low-dose. We cannot, however, state that Derivative is better than curcumin, since there wasn't a comparative study carried out in the same animal model and under the same experimental conditions [45].

The toxicity of these compounds was also evaluated using the Alamar Blue assay on a murine microglial cell line (BV-2). It was observed that curcumin and derivative 1 did not exhibit cytotoxicity, unlike derivative 4, which was toxic at concentrations above 1.25 μ M (unpublished data). These results suggest that while the tert-butoxide group enhances AD-related effects, it may act as a toxicophore. Additionally, the ester group, as previously mentioned, can easily be converted into a carboxyl group in the body through hydrolysis by esterases. Thus, a good optimization strategy would be to replace this group with a bioisostere group with a similar size or molecular volume and comparable biological properties.

4.3 Docking of Curcumin and derivatives 1 and 4 with A β 40 and A β 42

To evaluate and compare the binding affinities of curcumin and its derivatives 1 and 4 toward A β peptides, a molecular docking study was performed using both A β 40 and A β 42. This was done to assess the potential of these compounds to interact with the peptides and consequently disaggregate or reduce A β aggregates. Additionally, a new compound, BF1, was tested. BF1 is structurally similar to derivative 4 but contains a disubstituted amide group with two methyl groups instead of an ester linked to the central carbon of the α,β -unsaturated diketone. This modification follows a previously mentioned suggestion to replace the ester group with a hydrolysis-resistant bioisostere.

According to the docking results with A β 40, curcumin exhibited the highest binding affinity, followed by compound BF1. In contrast, derivative 4 showed the lowest binding affinity. In its highest-affinity pose, this compound forms only two hydrogen bonds with the ILE31 residue.

The SeeSAR software includes a feature called Hyde Coloring, which allows for the visualization of each atom's contribution to the overall binding affinity. The Hyde scoring function (short for Hydration and Dehydration) calculates what happens to both the ligand and the target protein upon interaction. For instance, the methoxy group oxygen in derivative 4 incurs a penalty of 4.1 kJ/mol (for the ligand part alone) due to desolvation. However, once this oxygen interacts with A β , it can form favorable interactions that recover 5.1 kJ/mol in binding free energy. The net result is a positive contribution of 2.7 kJ/mol, reflecting an increase in binding affinity.

This feature uses colored spheres to represent these contributions: green spheres indicate favorable (positive) contributions to binding affinity, while red spheres indicate unfavorable (negative) contributions, often due to steric hindrance. In Figure 3, it can be observed that the carbonyl oxygen of the ester group contributes negatively to the binding affinity, which explains why derivative 4 has the lowest affinity for the A β 40 peptide. On the other hand, the amide group in BF1 contributes positively to the affinity, making BF1 the compound with the highest binding potential among the derivatives—excluding curcumin.

Figure 4. Characterization of binding affinity Derivative 4 - A β 40.

According to the results obtained with A β 42, there is no significant difference in binding affinity among the tested compounds. However, in this case, derivative 4 exhibits the highest affinity, followed by derivative 1. The compound with the lowest affinity is BF1.

In this scenario, the ester group contributes positively to the binding affinity by forming a hydrogen bond with the HIS514 residue, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 5. Characterization of binding affinity Derivative 4 - A β 42.

Table 3. Affinity results, obtained through SeeSAR.					
	Compounds	Affinity [M]	MW	LogP	TPSA
Aβ40	Curcumin	2,80e ⁻⁶	368,4	3,37	93,06
	Derivative 1	2,45e ⁻⁵	368,4	3,37	93,06
	Derivative 4	1,62e ⁻⁴	482,5	4,33	119,36
	Compound BF1	6,15e ⁻⁶	453,5	3,07	113,37

Table 4. Affinity results, obtained through SeeSAR.					
	Compounds	Affinity [M]	MW	LogP	TPSA
Aβ42	Curcumin	6,11e ⁻⁷	368,4	3,37	93,06
	Derivative 1	4,82e ⁻⁷	368,4	3,37	93,06
	Derivative 4	2,51e ⁻⁷	482,5	4,33	119,36
	Compound BF1	9,34e ⁻⁷	453,5	3,07	113,37

5. Conclusion

Despite considerable progress in understanding Alzheimer's disease (AD), finding an effective treatment remains difficult. Current therapies mainly aim to alleviate symptoms, with cholinesterase inhibitors and NMDA receptor antagonists offering only limited benefits. Curcumin has been studied as therapeutic compound, as it targets numerous pathways, and given its remarkable antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-A β aggregation activities, it is a compound with significant therapeutic potential in the context of Alzheimer's disease (AD).

In recent decades, extensive research has been conducted on curcumin and its natural and synthetic analogs to improve its pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties for various diseases. In this study multiple Structure-Activity Relationships described in literature were reported and compared with physicochemical properties predicted using Swiss ADME, and results of *in chemico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies.

In future research, and based on the discussed structure-activity relationships, it would be valuable to design new curcumin derivatives with better bioavailability and better efficacy in AD. The proposed structural modifications would lead to novel curcumin derivatives which should undergo testing to evaluate their activity against AD and determine whether they offer improvements compared to curcumin and compounds such as derivatives 1 and 4. Furthermore, investigating these derivatives

will help validate the previously established structure-activity relationships and identify those with the greatest potential, paving the way for the discovery of new pharmacophores in the context of AD.

6. References

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